

MIXED-MODE DELAMINATION IN A CARBON-FIBRE COMPOSITE LAMINATE UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

N. Blanco¹, E. K. Gamstedt², L. E. Asp³ and J. Costa¹

¹ *AMADE – Anàlisi i Materials Avançats pel Disseny Estructural, EPS-University of Girona, Avda. Lluís Santaló, s/n, E-17071 Girona, Spain*

² *Department of Solid Mechanics, Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), S-100 44 Stockholm, Sweden*

³ *IFP SICOMP AB, Composite Materials Division, S-431 22 Mölndal, Sweden*

SUMMARY: Delamination readily forms after impact on composite laminates. If the composite structure is thereafter subjected to fatigue loading, the delamination will most likely propagate and ultimately lead to out-of-plane buckling and final failure. Many composite components have curved shapes, tapered thickness and plies with different orientations, which will make the delamination grow with a mode mix that depends on the length of the delamination. In this investigation, fatigue crack propagation has been characterized in essentially unidirectional laminates of carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy in a mixed-mode bending (MMB) fixture with constant mode mix, as well as with double-cantilever beam (DCB) in mode I and an end-notched flexure (ENF) test for mode II. The parameters of Paris law were determined for mode I, mode II and mixed mode. Mode III was not investigated. Both the coefficient and exponent in Paris law were found to depend non-monotonically on the mode mix, G_{II}/G , unlike most models in the literature which assume a monotonic and linear relationship between these parameters and the mode mix. Delamination propagation was also characterized in mixed-mode end-loaded split (MMELS). These data were compared with predictions based on the characterized parameters from the MMB tests. It was found that the improved non-monotonic model for the Paris law parameters resulted in better predictions than previously suggested growth formulae. Possible reasons for the dependency of the crack propagation rates on the degree of mode mix are briefly discussed.

KEYWORDS: delamination, fatigue, carbon-fibre composite, mixed-mode, Paris law

INTRODUCTION

Most of the failures of structural elements in service are a consequence of the mechanical fatigue. Fatigue must be a decisive factor for a durable design of mechanical elements. In laminated composite materials the fatigue process involves different damage modes that produce the degradation of the material. An important damage mode is the delamination of the plies of the laminate. In aeronautical applications, composite plates are sensitive to impact. If the composite structure is subsequently loaded in compression, delaminations are likely to grow in varying crack mode and eventually cause structural failure by buckling [1]. Compressive fatigue after impact is a critical scenario. Methods to characterize subcritical fatigue delamination growth in mixed mode are therefore of importance. Suitable inspection intervals could then be predicted with higher accuracy. Delaminations generally grow in mixed mode. The mode mix is likely to change during the course of delamination fatigue growth e.g. because of varying plate thickness and curved composite panels. In the present investigation, delamination growth in virtually unidirectional carbon-fibre composite has been investigated in mode I, mode II and mixed mode I/II. The mode III contribution in delamination growth is typically quite small for composite structures because of the constraints of adjacent plies and the fact that the critical energy-release-rate values are higher for mode III than for the other modes. The propagation rates have been characterized in terms of Paris-law plots for three different constant mode combinations in well-controlled tests. Suitable models for the Paris law parameters have then been explored. Finally, the growth law parameters have been compared with propagation

data for another test with a geometry and loading that give rise to a mode mix that varies as the delamination grows. Some suggestions of how to generalise the empirical growth law formulations are also given.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

A series of tests were carried out to characterize the delamination growth in different mixed modes under fatigue conditions. Basically these tests caused propagation under fatigue from an initial delamination, or pre-crack, in beam-type specimens. All the specimens were manufactured according to the supplier's recommended procedures from unidirectional HTA/6376C carbon-epoxy prepreg produced by Hexcel. The elastic properties of the cured plies are summarised in Table 1. The average thickness of the cured plies was 0.131 mm and a 7.5 μm thick Upilex[®] 7.5S polyamide film from UBE was used as starter crack.

Table 1. Elastic properties for the composite material

E_{11}	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12}=G_{13}$	G_{23}
120 GPa	10.5 GPa	0.30	0.51	5.25 GPa	3.48 GPa

For mode I crack growth, a double cantilever beam (DCB) test was used. For mode II, an end-notched flexure (ENF) test was chosen, and for constant mixed mode I/II, a mixed-mode bending (MMB) test was employed. Details of how the experiments at constant mode mix were carried out can be found in Ref. 2. Crack propagation tests with a slightly varying degree of mode mix were carried out with a mixed-mode end-loaded split (MMELS) test. The MMELS test is a variation of the mode II end load split (ELS) test where the external load is only applied to one of the specimen's arms. Figure 1 schematically represents the test set-up for the MMELS. A sliding clamp end is used in order to avoid a axial loads as the specimen bends.

Figure 1. Mixed-mode end-loaded split test

This type of test has been analysed by Hashemi *et al.* [3] and Kinloch *et al.* [4]. Their analysis is based on first order beam theory and includes some correction factors to adjust the predictions to the experimental results and take into account the anisotropy of the material. Although this approach accounts for a variation on the mode mix as the delamination grows, the authors consider this variation almost negligible and refer to this test as fixed-ratio mixed-mode (FRMM). Bao *et al.* [5] have also analysed this type of test among others. Their approach is based on an orthotropic rescaling technique in combination with formulae that give the best fit to finite element solutions. The expressions of Bao and co-workers for the MMELS test are presented in the following (see reference 5 for a more detailed explanation). The total energy release rate and the mode I energy release rate for a unidirectional composites are

$$G = \frac{6P^2}{E_1 b^2 h_1^3} \left[1 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\eta} \right)^{-3} \right] \left[a + Y(1 + F(1 - \eta)) \lambda^{\frac{1}{4}} h_1 \right]^2 \quad (1)$$

$$G_I = \frac{AP^2}{E_1 b^2 h_1^3} \left[a + Y_1 (1 + F_1 (1 - \eta)) \lambda^{\frac{1}{4}} h_1 \right]^2 \quad (2)$$

respectively, where E_1 is the Young's modulus in the fibre direction and λ is a material parameter, b is the width of the specimen, h_1 is the thickness of the specimen's arm where the load P is applied, η is the thickness ratio of both specimen's arms and a is the delamination length. The expressions for the Y , F , A , Y_1 and F_1 factors can be found in reference 5.

The specimens used for the MMELS test were 20 mm width and their effective length was $L=150$ mm. Two different stacking sequences were considered, $[0_s//(\pm 5, 0_8)_s]$ and $[0_{20}//(\pm 5, 0_8)_s]$, corresponding to the thickness ratios $\eta = 0.25$ and $\eta = 1$, respectively. The sign “//” refers to the plane of the artificial delamination, as can be seen in Figure 2. The ± 5 plies were included in order to reduce the fibre bridging at delamination growth. In the case of cross-over fibre bridging, the growth conditions at the crack tip are the same as those for an unbridged crack [6]. Since the understanding of crack propagation of unbridged cracks is a prerequisite to address the more general case of bridged cracking, only unbridged fatigue delamination is considered here.

Figure 2. Stacking sequence and initial crack for the MMELS test specimens

Considering the total energy release rate as the sum of the energy release rates in mode I and mode II (mode III is deemed negligible) and taking into account the expressions (1) and (2), the mix mode variation for a growing delamination can be calculated. Figure 3 shows the mix mode variation for the MMELS test specimens as the delamination grows.

To ensure a maximum variation of the mode mix, short initial delaminations were used. In the tests included pre-cracks, a_0 , were about 2.5 and 9.5 mm for the $\eta = 0.25$ and $\eta = 1$ specimens, respectively. It should be mentioned here that the use of such small pre-cracks increases the difficulty in obtaining valid fatigue delamination data as the experiment tends to be unstable.

Figure 3. Mix mode variation for the MMELS test after Bao *et al.* [5] approach

To ascertain that the external load is effectively applied to the midplane of the cantilever beam, a special kind of hinges was used to apply the load for the DCB, MMB and ENF tests [7]. With conventional hinges of piano type, the energy release rate would be difficult to estimate for short cracks due to the eccentrically applied load. In the case of the MMELS test a variation of this type of hinges was used in order to ensure this condition in both specimen geometries. Figure 4 shows the hinge used in MMELS test.

Figure 4. Mixed-mode end-loaded split test

The delamination length was measured in-situ in the tensile machine with a moving microscope focussed on the edge of the specimen. Delamination cracks are known to form a thumb-nail shaped crack front in mode I (cf. Schön *et al.* [8]). Nevertheless, because of experimental necessity, the crack length along the edge surface was used in the analysis as a crack length to an effective planar front. For mixed mode fatigue delaminations this error is deemed to be small compared with scatter in measurements. For larger contributions of mode II, delaminations fronts have been observed to become increasingly planar [2].

FATIGUE DELAMINATION MODELLING

MONOTONIC MODEL

The well-known Paris law is the most common method used to model the fatigue crack growth. In its simplest expression the Paris law can be expressed as:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta G_{tot})^r \quad (3)$$

where da/dN stands for the propagation rate of the delamination, being a the delamination length and N the number of cycles, ΔG_{tot} for the total energy release rate range and C and r are propagation parameters that must be determined experimentally. In this expression ΔG_{tot} does not take into account the individual contribution of the different modes. In the literature other empirical expressions of the same law can be found, where the relative contributions of mode I and mode II are considered [9-12]. In these approaches the propagation rate is obtained either as a combination of the individual propagation rates for each individual mode or with a combination of the propagation parameters C and r according to a linear rule of mixtures. Kenane *et al.* [13] based on their studies on glass/epoxy laminates propose a modification of the Paris law where the propagation parameters depend on the amount of energy release rate in mode II over the total (G_{II}/G) in a non-linear way.

Based on the study of laminated materials and bi-materials, Hutchinson and Suo [14] define the mode mixity, ψ , as a function of the stress intensity factors in mode I and mode II as:

$$\psi = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{K_{II}}{K_I}\right) \quad (4)$$

Assuming that the fracture toughness of the interface between the plies where de delamination grows depends on the mixity ratio, Hutchinson and Suo describe the variation of the critical energy release rate of the interface as:

$$\Gamma_0(\psi) = \frac{G_{Ic}}{1 + \left(\frac{G_{Ic}}{G_{IIc}} - 1\right) \sin^2 \psi} \quad (5)$$

where G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are the critical energy release rate values for the material in mode I and mode II, respectively.

Based on the mode mixity defined in Equation (4), Andersons *et al.* [15] propose a modified Paris-law as a function of the individual stress intensity factors in the crack instead of the energy release rates combined with Palmgren-Miner's damage accumulation rule. The propagation parameters are also defined as functions of the mode mixity and the critical intensity factors for mode I and mode II. Kardomateas *et al.* [16] propose a propagation rate of the delamination where the propagation parameters, C and r , vary as function ψ . The modified Paris law suggested by Kardomateas and co-workers can be expressed as:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\psi) \frac{\Delta \hat{G}^{r(\psi)}}{1 - \hat{G}_{max}} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\hat{G} = \frac{G_{tot}}{\Gamma_0(\psi)} \quad (7)$$

and $\Delta \hat{G} = \hat{G}_{max} - \hat{G}_{min}$. The dependency of the propagation parameters C and r on the mixity ratio is given by:

$$C(\psi) = C_1 \left[1 + \left(\frac{C_{II}}{C_1} - 1 \right) \sin^2 \psi \right] \quad (8)$$

$$r(\psi) = r_1 \left[1 + \left(\frac{r_{II}}{r_1} - 1 \right) \sin^2 \psi \right] \quad (9)$$

where C_1 and r_1 are the propagation parameters for pure mode I and C_{II} and r_{II} for pure mode II.

NON-MONOTONIC MODEL

All the above commented models for the fatigue growth of a delamination in a composite material take into account a variation of the propagation parameters C and r in a monotonic way. Nevertheless, considering the experiments carried out in mode I, mode II and constant mode mix by Asp *et al.* [2] a non-monotonic variation of these parameters is found. This non-monotonic behaviour of the parameters can also be found taking into account the results of the experiments carried out in a carbon/epoxy laminate by Tanaka and Tanaka [17].

This non-monotonic variation cannot be well described by any of the previous models as they only consider one fitting parameter in their expressions. For a better description of the non-monotonic variation of the propagation parameters generalized expressions with at least two experimentally adjusted factors are justified.

Here a set of parabolic equations is suggested to obtain the propagation parameters. These expressions must take proportionality of mode I and mode II into account. In this case, the common ratio of mode II energy release rate over the total energy release rate is considered. The expressions for both parameters are given by:

$$\log C = c_1 + c_2 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G} \right) + c_3 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

$$r = r_1 + r_2 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G} \right) + r_3 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G} \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

From the above expressions and considering the case where the delamination propagates under pure mode I, it can be easily found that $c_1 = C_1$ and $r_1 = r_1$.

Since the critical energy release rate values, G_c , as reported by Asp *et al.* [2] in mode I, mode II and mode mix I/II, a variation of G_c depending on the mix mode can be introduced. A similar behaviour was also found by Greenhalgh *et al.* [18] for different composite materials. Analogous to expressions (10) and (11), a parabolic function depending on the ratio G_{II}/G is introduced:

$$G_c = g_1 + g_2 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G} \right) + g_3 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

As before, if only a mode I growing of the delamination, it can be found that $g_1 = G_{Ic}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 5 and 6 represent the variation of the propagation parameters with the mode mixity, according to references 2 and 17, respectively. In both figures the expected results for expressions of Kardomateas are included to serve as a comparison between the experimental results and the monotonic approaches.

Figure 5. Comparison of propagation parameters for experimental values of Asp *et al.* [2]

Figure 6. Comparison of propagation parameters for experimental values of Tanaka and Tanaka [17]

The fatigue tests under mode I, mode II and constant mixed-mode were carried out under constant amplitude displacement. The detailed results can be found in reference 2. Figure 7 summarises the results in a log-log plot of the crack propagation rate, da/dN , versus the normalised total energy release rate for the DCB, ENF and MMB tests. Also shown in this figure are straight lines adjusted to the experimental points by least-square fits.

In Figure 7 can be seen that the propagation parameters C and r vary with the mix mode in a non-monotonic way. The coefficient C corresponds to the intercept of the straight line, and the exponent r refers to the slope of the line. The constants C and r for the MMB test do not lay in between the C and r values for mode I and mode II. This implies that the propagation rate of the delamination depends on the mix mode in a non-monotonic way. At this point an expression of the Paris-law taking this non-monotonic variation of the parameters is introduced. The proposed expression is given by:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = D \left(\frac{\Delta G_{\text{tot}}}{G_c} \right)^r \quad (13)$$

where the parameters D , r and G_c depend on the mix mode according to (10), (11) and (12), respectively. The coefficient is now denoted D to discriminate between the two Paris law expressions (3) and (13), where D has the unit mm/cycle whereas the unit for C depends on the value of the exponent r . In Table 2, the values of these parameters for the present material are presented.

Figure 7. Crack propagation rate vs. normalised strain energy release rate for DCB, MMB and ENF tests after Asp *et al.* [2]

The non-linear and non-monotonic behaviour should be explained by the micro-mechanisms involved in the delamination growth. In mode I less friction between the arms of the specimen is observed, meanwhile in mode II this is a predominant mechanism. In reference 2, a fractographic analysis showed a major presence of matrix rollers for the mode II specimens. Mode II is also known for the formation of shear cusps in front of the crack tip that finally coalesce to increase the delamination length [19]. Although the present lay-up has been designed to prevent fibre bridging, its presence cannot be ruled out. How these micro-mechanisms combine and interact is not a well-known process, but there is no reason to believe that it should follow a linear and monotonic way for propagation rates.

For the MMELS test similar procedures were followed during the testing. Due to the unstable behaviour of this kind of test, especially for short delamination lengths, just some specimens could be tested under fatigue conditions and the applied load-displacement had to be manually re-adjusted to avoid the propagation of the delamination under static conditions. Figure 8 shows the delamination length versus the number of cycles for one of the tested specimens. The scatter in propagation behaviour between specimens was considerable.

Figure 8. Crack length versus number of cycles for a MMELS test

Table 2. Paris law parameters for delamination in unidirectional HTA/6376C at different mode mixities

Test:	DCB	MMB	ENF
G_{II}/G	0	0.5	1
D (mm/cycle)	2.21×10^{-3}	1.68×10^{-1}	1.22×10^{-1}
r	5.09	6.28	4.38
G_c (J/m ²)	260	447	1002

In the MMELS test, the mode mix is changing continuously. However, the variation is small enough, especially for large cracks length, to consider that in a log-log plot the experimental propagation rate, da/dN , versus the normalised total energy release rate will lay in an almost straight line. Figure 9 corresponds to this plot for the same specimen as in Figure 8 which in turn is the one which best fits this condition and has the least scatter in the results.

Figure 9. Crack propagation rate vs. normalised strain energy release rate for a MMELS test

It can be seen that the simulated propagation rate based on experimental data carried out in constant-mixed mode overestimates the propagation rate in the MMELS test, and therefore serves as a conservative prediction. The scatter between specimens was quite large, especially during growth of short cracks. Despite these imperfections, the proposed scheme to predict crack growth from constant mixed-mode tests seem to be a viable path to predict growth during more general conditions. A statistical approach would however be necessary since the variability in data is significant. Methods to account for a variable mode-mix during delamination growth have been presented.

CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue delamination growth has been characterized in constant mixed mode at different mixities. The Paris law parameters turned out vary non-monotonically with the degree of mode mixity, which is generally not taken into account in existing methodologies growth rate predictions. A generalized model to account for this non-monotonic dependency on mode mixity is presented, and applied to data from a mixed-mode end-loaded split test. The predictions show only a fair correspondence with the experimental results, although the predictions were conservative.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Mr. Hans Öberg for able help in fatigue testing with the MMELS fixture and Mr. Sören Nilsson at the Swedish Defence Research Agency (FOI) for manufacturing and supplying the test specimens. Financial support from Spanish Government (MAT2000-0741-C02-01),

the Swedish Research Council (VR) and the Swedish Defence Materiel Administration (FMV) are acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. K.-F. Nilsson, L. E. Asp, J. E. Alpmann and L. Nystedt, "Delamination buckling and growth for delaminations at different depths in a slender composite panel", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 38, 3039-3071 (2001).
2. L. E. Asp, A. Sjögren and E. Greenhalgh, "Delamination growth and thresholds in a carbon/epoxy composite under fatigue loading", *Journal of Composites Technology and Research*, 23, 55-68 (2001).
3. S. Hashemi, A. J. Kinloch and J. G. Williams, "The analysis of interlaminar fracture in uniaxial fibre-polymer composites", *Proceedings of the Royal Society, London A*, 427, 173-199 (1990).
4. A. J. Kinloch, Y. Wang, J. G. Williams and P. Yayla, "The mixed-mode delamination of fibre composite materials", *Composites Science and Technology*, 47, 225-237 (1993).
5. G. Bao, S. Ho, Z. Suo and B. Fan, "The role of material orthotropy in fracture specimens for composites", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 29, 1105-1116 (1992).
6. B. F. Sørensen and T. K. Jacobsen, "Crack growth in composites - Applicability of R-curves and bridging laws", *Plastics Rubber and Composites*, 29, 119-133 (2000).
7. F. Brandt, "New load introduction concept for improved and simplified delamination beam testing", *Experimental Techniques*, 22, 17-20 (1998).
8. J. Schön, T. Nyman, A. Blom and H. Ansell, "A numerical and experimental investigation of delamination behaviour in the DCB specimen", *Composites Science and Technology*, 60, 173-184 (2000).
9. R. L. Ramkumar and J. D. Whitcomb, "Characterization of mode I and mixed-mode delamination growth in T300/5208 graphite/epoxy", *Delamination and Debonding of Materials*, ASTM STP 876, 315-335 (1985).
10. C.-G. Gustafson and M. Hojo, "Delamination fatigue crack growth in unidirectional graphite/epoxy laminates", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 6, 36-52 (1987).
11. A. J. Russell and K. N. Street, "Predicting interlaminar fatigue crack growth rates in compressively loaded laminates", *Delamination and Debonding of Materials*, ASTM STP 1012, 162-178 (1989).
12. C. Dahlem and G. S. Springer, "Delamination growth in composites under cyclic loads", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 28, 732-781 (1994).
13. M. Kenane and M. L. Benzeggagh, "Mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites under fatigue loading", *Composites Science and Technology*, 57, 597-605 (1997).
14. J. W. Hutchinson and Z. Suo, "Mixed mode cracking in layered materials", *Advances in Applied Mechanics*, 29, 63-191 (2001).
15. J. Andersons, M. Hojo and S. Ochiai, "Model of delamination propagation in brittle-matrix composites under cyclic loading", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 20, 431-450 (2001).
16. G. A. Kardomateas, A. A. Pelegri and B. Malik, "Growth of internal delaminations under cyclic compression in composite plates", *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, 43, 847-868 (1995).
17. H. Tanaka and K. Tanaka, "Mixed-mode growth of interlaminar cracks in carbon/epoxy laminates under cyclic loading", *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 1, 181-189 (1995).
18. E. Greenhalgh, L. Asp and S. Singh, "Delamination resistance, failure criteria and fracture morphology of 0°/0°, 0°/5° and 0°/90° ply interfaces in CFRP", *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Deformation and Fracture of Composites*, (1999).
19. S. Singh and E. Greenhalgh, "Micromechanisms of interlaminar fracture in carbon fibre reinforced plastics at multidirectional ply interfaces under static and cyclic loading", *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, 27, 220-226 (1998).